

INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES FOR IMPROVING STUDENTS' SPIRITUAL AND MORAL COMPETENCIES OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM

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Аннотация. В статье изложены идеи об интерактивных технологиях совершенствования духовно-нравственных компетенций студентов в процессе внеаудиторных занятий, регулировании образовательных отношений, саморазвитии, а также повышении собственной духовно-нравственной компетентности.

Ключевые слова: концепция педагогической науки, студенты, духовно-нравственное воспитание, методика, совершенствование, духовно-нравственная компетентность.

Annotation. The article presents ideas about interactive technologies for improving students' spiritual and moral competencies in extracurricular activities, regulating educational relations, self-development, and improving their own spiritual and moral competence.

Keywords: the concept of pedagogical science, students, spiritual and moral education, methodology, improvement, spiritual and moral competence.

Main part. Pedagogical science deals with the most pressing issues of the field and its important branch, pedagogical anthropology and social psychology. Therefore, one of the important challenges facing pedagogy today is conducting extensive research in the field of social pedagogy and social psychology.

Pedagogical science should comprehensively study and scientifically substantiate the relationship between the level of education and upbringing, the moral character of an individual, ways and regularities of sociocorrection, and a person's intellectual capabilities.

The organization of the process of self-education, knowledge and intellectual development of students and pupils requires the pedagogical science to make extensive use of the following methods in order to accurately determine the impact of existing trends on personal development, moral qualities, and worldview:

1. Social surveying.
2. Interviewing.
3. Questionnaire.
4. Observation.
5. Conducting sociological research.
6. Statistics.
7. Pedagogical diagnostics.

In this process, the pedagogical discipline should work directly in connection with social psychology. This is because social psychology is an important aspect of social consciousness.

This aspect of social consciousness is characterized by the mood, customs, interests, and needs of members of society.

While the field of pedagogy provides the methods, means, laws, and principles for organizing the educational process, it primarily takes into account the psychological state of the student.

Figure 1.

Types of interactive technologies and their educational advantages

Interactive Technology	Form of Implementation	Educational Outcome
Debates and Discussions	Group discussions on social and moral topics	Expressing opinions, listening, moral reasoning
Role-playing	Staging real-life situations	Conscience-based choices, empathy, personal responsibility
Case Study (situation analysis)	Analysis of moral issues (e.g., honesty, friendship)	Analyzing, applying moral criteria
Trainings and Psychological Exercises	Communication, self-awareness, emotional maturity	Self-awareness, emotional intelligence, intrinsic motivation
Moral and Educational Excursions	Museum, shrine, theatrical excursions	Historical memory, respect for values
Creative Projects	Essay, stage performances, social video	Creativity, expressing moral ideas
Volunteer Activities	Orphanage, environmental actions	Generosity, compassion, social responsibility

Nowadays, the educational process alone is not sufficient for shaping the moral and ethical development of students. Extracurricular activities create broad opportunities in this regard. The modern concept of the pedagogical discipline aims to develop the student's personality comprehensively, ensure active participation in social life, and strengthen moral values through practical activities.

Extracurricular educational activities:

- teach based on personal examples and real-life situations
- develop the student's experience in making moral decisions
- enhance the sense of teamwork, compassion, and responsibility among young people

Forms of activities. Circles and club activities: the "Spirituality and Enlightenment" circle, the youth leadership school, and the "Moral Choice" club sessions.

Social initiatives: "Youth Week," "Moral Ambassador" competitions, student forums.

Voluntary and community work: student support groups, environmental awareness campaigns, flash mobs on moral topics. Flash mobs on moral topics are quick, public, and interactive actions organized to promote social and moral values and to awaken spiritual and moral consciousness among students or young people.

Pedagogical conditions. For moral and ethical interactive education to be effective: there must be a free and open environment, the teacher should approach the student as a partner, education based on internal understanding and choice should be prioritized over external control, and activities should encourage independent thinking and ethical decision-making. Using interactive technologies in extracurricular activities allows students not only to become knowledgeable but also to develop the ability to make ethical decisions, and to grow as active, conscientious, and well-rounded individuals in society. Through these methods, teachers can instill high virtues such as humanity, kindness, honesty, and dedication into the hearts of the younger generation.

Methods of education are the ways of interaction among educators, aimed at achieving the most effective results in education and development. Through these methods, educational goals are realized, the content of activities emerges, worldview and moral knowledge are provided, each learner is engaged in active participation, and behavior in accordance with societal requirements is formed.

Aspects considered when choosing educational methods:

1. Consistency of methods:
2. Formation of perception (concept, judgment, belief, evaluation).
3. Organizing activities and forming social behavior experience (practice, task, etc.).
4. Encouraging activity and behavior (competition, incentives, punishment).

The coordination of methods is carried out by the group leader, group activists, and the student community. The transformation of educational methods into self-education methods: Beliefs turn into forming self-belief, exercises turn into practicing self-exercise, etc. In groups, educational methods are applied both by the group leader, the tutor, and through the interaction of the student community. Factors influencing the selection of methods:

1. The purpose and content of education.
2. The level of students' upbringing.
3. The level of interpersonal relationships.
4. The teacher's authority and experience.
5. The age and individual characteristics of students.

Methodology. It is recommended to use methods in a comprehensive manner to improve results. The directions of the activities of learners include collective activity and personal activity.

Group of educational methods (according to the research of L.I. Amanbayeva):

1. Methods aimed at educating collective life are distinguished by the generality of pedagogical requirements, methods and forms of self-management, traditions, games, and hopefulness (plans for the future).

2. Methods of individual influence on a person consist of explanation, requirement, demonstration, punishment, and encouragement.

The choice of forms of the educational process depends on the content of educational work, the age of students, the skills of educators, and the conditions of upbringing.

Example of educational work: Experimental work on the spiritual and educational upbringing of students was conducted at Urgench State Pedagogical Institute, Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute, and Namangan State University.

The purpose of this work:

- restoring and transmitting spiritual heritage.
- spreading values and new ideas.
- establishing dialogue-based communication between students and educational institution-community organizations.

1. Methods used at work:

Organizing the team and self-organization:

- team games
- team self-management
- team self-service
- uniform requirements

2. Methods of constant and purposeful communication:

- friendly, trustworthy relationships in ordinary and extraordinary situations
- social protection, respect
- pedagogical demand, persuasion, warning, criticism
- trust, empathy, decision-making, problem situations

3. Methods of personal activity:

- self-analysis and understanding.
- self-discipline (controlling emotions and intellect).
- self-motivation (controlling willpower and behavior).

4. Pedagogical and psychological methods of influence:

- correcting a person's consciousness and behavior.
- encouraging or stopping activity.
- addressing the individual in life situations.
- explanation, creating a successful environment, awakening hopes and aspirations, practice, encouragement, punishment.
- cognitive direction - forming the necessary competencies for students to acquire moral-educational, scientific, technical, and social knowledge, skills, and abilities.

In modern education, effective educational technologies are a set of methods and tools that directly influence the development of a student's personality, their consciousness, moral stance, and motivation. Through these technologies, a student:

- expresses their thoughts freely,
- makes moral decisions,
- strives to be beneficial to society,
- acquires competencies more deeply.

Effective technologies used in spiritual and moral education.

The most effective educational technologies, based on the following methodological recommendations, are presented:

Figure 2.

Effective technologies used in spiritual and moral education

Type of technology	Description and impact
Dialogic learning	Thinking based on moral dialogue between teacher and student and among students.
Problem-based learning	Moral dilemmas encourage critical thinking.
Role-playing technology	It shapes empathy and moral stance through vital social roles.
"Bouquet of thoughts"	Students developed various ideas about moral values.
Working in small groups	Through cooperation, virtues such as respect, responsibility, and solidarity develop.
Digital technologies (multimedia, video)	Visual moral materials have an emotional impact.

Directions for application based on methodological recommendations.

1. Reviewing educational programs: - Each subject's curriculum should include spiritual-moral competence (integrative approach). - For example, in pedagogy: spiritual-moral culture; in history: national pride, honesty; in psychology: national moral mindset, and so on.

2. Preparing didactic materials: - ethical situational tasks - analysis based on literary texts - test and diagnostic questions.

Implementing pedagogical monitoring:

- developing rubrics (assessment criteria) to evaluate growth in moral decision-making.
- observing personal development through self-analysis and portfolios.

Conclusion. Based on integrating modern technologies with national values, Uzbekistan's national-spiritual values (honesty, compassion, consequence, patriotism) can be effectively highlighted through digital educational tools (video clips, QR-coded assignments, quizzes).

For example:

1. Moral video clip: "Honesty is great wealth" (questions and answers based on the clip).
2. QR-code task: students solve a moral problem through a mobile application.
3. Tests via Google Forms or Moodle to assess moral literacy levels.

Methodically implementing effective educational technologies helps students develop moral and ethical competencies, increases educational effectiveness, and contributes to the comprehensive development of the student's personality.

For this reason, every educator should appropriately and systematically select modern methods and technologies according to the goal.

List of references

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining "Uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash va uni amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi 2019 - yil 31-dekabrda 1059-son Qarori. <https://lex.uz/docs/-4676839>
2. Abdullayeva M.R. Talabalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy kompetensiyalarini pedagogika fani konsepsiyasi asosida takomillashtirishning pedagogik-psixologik omillari. "Til va adabiyot ta'limi" ilmiy-metodik jurnal. 2025-yil, may 9-son 289-290 betlar.
3. Abdullayeva M.R. Talabalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy kompetensiyalarini pedagogika fani konsepsiyasi asosida takomillashtirishning nazariy asoslari. // "Pedagogika". Nizomiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal.03/2025. 137-141 betlar.
4. Salayeva M.S. Umumiy pedagogika. [Matn]: darslik / –Toshkent: "Nodirabegim" nashriyoti, 2021.- 598 b.
5. Salayeva M.S., Yusufzoda Sh.Y., Abdullayeva M.R., Yo'ldosheva S.A. Tarbiyaviy ishlar metodikasi [Matn]: darslik / –Toshkent: "ZUXRO BARAKA BIZNES" nashriyoti 2026. – 279 b.